

Biological efficacy, cost, and mammalian toxicity of insecticides recommended for rice in the Philippines

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More than 50 commercial insecticides are sold in the Philippines, but only 15 are currently registered for use on rice. For an insecticide to be registered the chemical company manufacturing it must submit data on its performance against each insect pest for review by an inter-agency committee composed of government officials. Factors that affect registration are efficacy, human safety (during application and residues at harvest), and effect on non-target organisms such as fish and animals. Once the criteria are satisfied for each insecticide, the company sets a price on the retail product. If approved, the price is used as a basis for credit costing in the government's Masagana 99 rice production programs. IRRI has evaluated insecticides against the major rice insect pests in the Philippines since 1962; evaluation data are available to any chemical company or national program that wishes to use them for product registration. IRRI annually publishes the Insecticide Evaluation Report, a compilation of all the chemical control experiments performed that year. The publication is available on request from the IRRI Entomology Department. IRRI data have been used extensively in the development of the list of recommended insecticides for rice in the Philippines. They cover the whorl maggot *Hydrellia philippina*, stem borer *Scirpophaga incertulas* and *Chilo suppressalis*, brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens*, whitebacked planthopper *Sogatella furcifera*, green leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens*, leaf folder *Cnaphalocrosis medinalis*, and rice bug *Leptocorisa oratorius*.

Sprayable and granular insecticides are evaluated at 0.75 kg a.i./ha and 1 kg a.i./ha dosages. The 1980 list of recommended insecticides in the Philippines shows that for each insect pest there is a wide range of chemicals to choose from in terms of cost and safety. The table lists the relative safety of the insecticides to the applicator, cost per application, and efficacy against the various rice insects

See table below

Efficacy, cost, and mammalian toxicity of insecticides recommended for rice in the Philippines, 1980.

Insecticide ^a	Formulation ^b	LD ₅₀ ^c		Cost ^d of application (\$/ha)	Efficacy ^e						
		Oral	Dermal		Whorl maggot	Stem borers	Brown plant-hopper	White-backed plant-hopper	Green leaf-hopper	Leaf folder	Rice bug
<i>Relatively safe sprayables</i>											
Acephate	75% WP	890	2000	30.0	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
MTMC	50% WP	600	1000	13.2	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
BPMC	50% EC, 50% WP	400	340	11.2	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
Carbaryl	85% WP	300	500	8.4	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
Diazinon	60% EC	300	460	18.4	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
<i>Moderately safe sprayables</i>											
MIPC	50% WP	180	500	11.1	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
Chlorpyrifos	15.8% EC	100	2000	39.9	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
Triazophos	40% EC	80	11000	31.0	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Endosulfan	35% EC	70	350	15.5	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>Dangerous sprayables</i>											
Carbofenthiion	48% EC	32	3100	13.2	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
Monocrotophos	30% EC	20	350	24.2	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Phosphamidon	50% EC	15	125	13.7	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
Azinphos-ethyl	40% EC	13	220	15.5	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	No
<i>Relatively safe granules</i>											
Diazinon	5% G, 6% G, 10% G	300	460	21.9	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No
<i>Moderately safe granules</i>											
γ-BHC	6% G	88	1000	9.9	No	Yes ^f	No	No	No	No	No
Endosulfan	5% G	70	350	13.3	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No
<i>Dangerous granules</i>											
Carbofuran	3% G	11	10220	37.0	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes ^g	Yes	Yes

^aDetermination of safety is based on oral LD₅₀ (mean lethal dose) values. ^bWP = wettable powder, EC = emulsifiable concentrate, G = granules. ^cTechnical (100%) insecticide. ^dSeptember 1979 retail prices, sprayables - 0.75 kg a.i./ha; granules - 1 kg a.i./ha. ^eEfficacy tests on whorl maggot and stem borers were conducted in the field. Whorl maggot efficacy = damage rating of 4 or less when control = 9; stem borer efficacy = significantly fewer dead-hearts than the control; brown planthopper efficacy was based on greenhouse and field trials where efficacy was ≥ 80% mortality in the greenhouse and > 60% mortality in the field; whitebacked planthopper, green leafhopper, leaf folder and rice bug efficacy was based on greenhouse trials where efficacy was > 80% mortality. Rice bug efficacy data from greenhouse trial were based on manufacturers' recommended dosages. ^fNot effective against the pink stem borer. ^gIf incorporated into the soil.